

Disseminating and Promoting Smart Farming Technologies – The Smart AKIS Network.

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Abstract

This paper summarises the early stages of the Smart AKIS project which aims to collect and disseminate Smart Farming Technologies (SFT) in line with farmers' needs. The methodology of collecting information and opinions from over 270 farmers from seven countries about SFTs is given. The methodology of collecting and analyzing the results of 718 scientific articles and 201 research projects to determine what the research topics and results are also outlined. Further information about the 164 SFT products that had been submitted by mid-January 2017 and entered into the inventory database are also summarized. There is outline information on how to submit research and product information to the inventory database on an on-going basis so that it can be promoted to end users (farmers, farming-advisors and contractors) and also seen by potential funders and collaborators for further product development and research collaboration which is also an objective of the Innovation Workshops which are starting in February 2017 around the seven countries.

1. Background and Introduction

The rapidly evolving Information and Communication Technologies have caused such a fast development in Smart Farming Technologies that researchers, equipment suppliers and certainly farmers and their advisers are struggling to keep up with the technologies available, whether commercially offered or completing the final stages of applied research projects. The self-sustaining Smart-AKIS network (www.smart-akis.com) has been designed for an effective exchange between industry, applied research, agricultural advisors and the farming community. The aim is that directly applicable solutions are widely disseminated and the grassroots needs and innovative ideas are comprehensively acquired. This will contribute to closing the divide between applied research and commercial innovation and will benefit the agricultural engineering and technology industry and the farming industry.

“Smart Farming Technologies” (SFT) covers the marketable, affordable, reliable and time-saving technologies developing from:

- farm management information systems,
- precision farming and
- agricultural automation and robotics.

The benefits are related to more efficient application of inputs, increased work speeds, comfort, improved decisions and enhanced flexibility.

The Smart AKIS project is the European Network on Smart Farming and will integrate aspects of the innovation processes and will lead to interactive, innovation-based, collaborations among researchers, developers and suppliers, advisors and farmers through multi-actor workshops.

AKIS is the acronym for Agricultural Knowledge and Information Systems, or Innovation Systems; both meanings are applicable in this project.

This paper outlines an early stage of the project with the following aspects:

- Collection and analysis of farmer SFT use and opinions,
- Collection and analysis of the existing, and impending, knowledge related to SFT a) from research and projects and also b) available from suppliers of SFT. Both sets of information are combined into an “inventory”
- Production of easily accessible end-user material for use by farmers and their advisors and
- Innovation support workshops to enable farmers and advisors, researchers and SFT suppliers and research funders to meet and discuss current useful developments, potential projects and supply and marketing networks.

This paper highlights particularly the farmer survey, industry solutions and research project results, and the on-going collection process for the Smart-AKIS inventory and provide background for applied researchers and suppliers of SFT.

The project goal is to enable the European farming community to regularly use Smart Farming Technologies and so bridge the gap between practice and research by identifying and delivering new Smart Farming solutions to fit farmers' needs.

The project of 13 partners from seven countries is supported by the EC Horizon 2020 program and the European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI). The project has a focused approach, concentrating on Smart Farming Technology for crop production. CEMA is a partner and with its national member Associations (including AXEMA) it ensures that there is a strong involvement of the machinery industry and the EurAgEng society, with 18 national societies (including SitmAfgr), brings in over 2000 European professional agricultural engineers.

Smart AKIS is aware that many Smart Farming solutions are available in the market now, but that many social and economic obstacles remain for the wider adoption of such technologies by farmers who increasingly demand that new solutions fit their requirements. As a Thematic Network, Smart AKIS adopts a multi-actor approach, targeting all stakeholders involved in agricultural innovation processes, such as farmers, farmer-associations, research organisations, advisory and extension services, agronomists and agricultural consultants, agricultural equipment suppliers and providers of smart farming solutions.

2. Methodologies

2.1 Farmer survey. The partners of Smart AKIS, led by the team at ZALF, prepared a comprehensive questionnaire¹ and surveyed more than 270 farmers and experts from all over Europe to understand and respond to the:

- Needs and interests of Smart Farming by farmers from France, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Serbia, Spain and UK and
- Factors hindering the adoption of Smart Farming in Europe.

2.2 Published research survey. Teams at the universities in Wageningen and Athens undertook a systematic review of literature collection methods before retrieving over 11000 articles². These articles were then manually assessed, over two rounds of filtering, to select only those relevant to SFT, using first the abstract, and then using the full article. The final selection was based upon those of practical relevance and in practical development. This led to about 718 articles being in the database with data from a further 201 EU research projects. An ongoing on-line survey is included for researchers to add to the database details of SFT research which is at an imminent stage for publication. This survey follows the EIP-Agri Common format for interactive innovation projects³.

2.3 Industry solutions survey. Following the format and analysis of "Published research survey" this survey was also promoted for industry solutions⁴. The survey was made available online to suppliers of SFT and promoted by various networks including FIWARE, FRACTALS and Smart Agrifood II as well as the project members, especially CEMA and EurAgEng. Contacts were also made with suppliers at precision farming events, agricultural machinery shows and similar events to encourage SFT suppliers to complete the survey and be added to the database. These personal contacts invariably needed an email to give further details of the project and its expected outcomes to highlight the advantages for SFT suppliers to be involved. As for the "Published research survey" the survey entries were added to a database for analysis.

2.4 Innovation support. Smart AKIS is holding Innovation Workshops, including to generate innovations and to assist the marketing and uptake of products and projects on Smart Farming in France, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Serbia, Spain and UK. Targeted at farmers and advisors, suppliers and researchers these dissemination, innovation and networking events will also encourage research funders and other investors to attend and help promote further R&D projects as well as marketing of commercially available Smart Farming Technologies for the end-users. The 21 Workshops will start from late February. A set of guidelines have been produced by Smart AKIS to help ensure that the workshops cover the project needs, build on best practice and produce analyzable outcomes.

Although a snap-shot of research and industry surveys has been taken for the current reports, submissions to both the research and industry (products) surveys for entry to the inventory database can be completed up to September 2018 by researchers and industry suppliers. The survey is given in the appendix of the reports^{2,4} and can be completed on-line via the Smart AKIS website.

3. Results and Discussion

By its nature this paper is a collection of the results from project reports and documents and much of the information below is taken directly from these, which should be referred to for greater detail and analysis.

3.1 Farmer survey.

The full results are available in a project report¹ and further analysis will be included in scientific papers. Much of this summary is also taken from a project summary briefing⁵.

Project partners interviewed more than 270 farmers from France, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Serbia, Spain and UK.

3.1.1 Current situation perceived by farmers.

- Crop disease reduction and soil conservation are farmers' main challenges but farmers are unsure whether smart farming can overcome them.
- Reducing harvest losses was considered most important in Greece (89%) and Serbia (90%). Reducing water use was also ranked as highly important in Greece (61%) and Serbia (74%) but surprisingly less important in Spain (50%).
- Farmers perceive the benefits of smart farming in terms of productivity and managing inputs rather than the environmental benefits.
- Private independent advisors, other farmers, and agri-tech providers are the three most important sources of information and support. Public extension and banks are least important.
- The most useful SFT are considered as 1) Robots for monotonous work processes (e.g. weeding, hoeing, harvesting), 2) Real-time diagnostics via drones, satellite imagery, or smart phone sensors, 3) Integration of various Smart Farming Technologies, and 4) Data for information and decision support.
- High cost and poor compatibility between devices and systems remain the main barriers for adoption.

3.1.2 Farmers views looking ahead

- Alliances with agro consultants might help a better penetration and adoption and Smart Farming as a service may fit farmers' needs. This is shown in the later research and industry surveys by contractors being a main user.
- Suppliers, consultants and advisors could usefully focus further on dissemination of existing technologies and the development of new ones on the farmers' main areas of interest: including Robots and Smart Equipment, remote diagnosis and monitoring and big data for farm management.
- Further adoption may be facilitated by lower cost, suitable equipment size, compatibility between equipment ("plug and play") and ease of use.

3.1.3 The main project ideas and needs captured from the survey include:

- GPS and similar devices (e.g. auto-steering) are mainly used in arable crops.
- Agricultural apps were selected more by vineyard and orchard farmers.
- Weather stations and soil moisture sensors with automatic data upload are more valuable for orchards and vineyards that rely on irrigation.
- Drones, mapping, and aerial imagery are potentially of more interest for arable growers.

Three-quarters of the farmers said they experiment on their farms. For example:

1. most frequently with equipment: building, adapting, and adjusting machinery to improve work processes;
2. testing new technologies and cropping patterns: including trying new varieties and rotations;
3. cultivation: including seeding, drilling, tillage, soil management and other management methods.

Over half of the farmers provided suggestions for existing SFT to make them more acceptable or useful. For example: improving access to SFT, the overall technological system, device level, data level, costs and compatibility.

3.2 Published research.

These findings and conclusions are shown by Wolters *et al*² and the main points are given here.

The total number of research related entries is 919 (as at January 2017); formed of 718 scientific articles and 201 research projects. The number of articles are growing quickly and the Technology Readiness Level most commonly

given (41%) is 5 (*Technology validated in relevant environment*) and fewer (29%) are in TRLs 7-9 (*System prototype demonstration in operational environment to Actual system proven in operational environment*).

The clear majority of research projects are investigating recording or mapping technologies to get more information on agronomic variables in the field. Research articles are more about farm management information systems or apps.

There are many field operations involving SFTs in projects and articles but scouting of crops or soil was the largest topic for articles (39% of those with a topic given) with irrigation and fertilizer application also very important.

Considering the keywords used as a way of classifying SFTs used in the research articles and in projects then machinery related or focusing on farming practices and / or production systems are most common. Plant production, fertilizer application and water- and soil management are also considered very important.

The applications for SFTs are similar for research articles and research projects. Many entries, 40% of scientific articles and 60% of research projects, focus on replacing an already existing technology but mostly this does not require a major change to an existing system. Significant learning is often required for the correct application of SFTs. In many situations, there is more than one purpose or application to a SFT and the effects of the SFTs can be observed directly by the farmer.

Regarding the application of SFTs, contractors were most often identified as the most likely users of SFTs.

Using SFTs often brings an increase in revenue, a reduction in stress and labour for the farmer and a reduction in energy use. A reduction in costs was often expected by implementing SFTs. There were also some improvements expected regarding environmental aspects.

SFT is in continuous development, it was seen that there is a tendency toward the scouting of crops and soils with information technology solutions. Regarding the application of SFT, research SFTs are often building on existing technology. Although significant learning is required this does not often lead to large time investments for farmers. The results of SFT are easy to observe. Both revenue and environmental aspects are of great importance in SFT development in the research sector.

3.3 Industry Solutions.

This information is from the second report by Wolters *et al*⁴ and shows a submission of 164 survey entries related to products (January 2017) and these can be classified mostly as recording or mapping tools. The development of farm management information systems and Apps is also an important group and is like the research entries². There are also many developments for variable rate technology. Slightly fewer entries were involved in guidance or controlled traffic farming technology or robotic systems. Overall, there is a consistent spread between the different classifications from 43 to 77 of the 164 in the five classifications.

Many products submitted can be used for fertilisation, disease control and pesticide application related operations. However very few SFTs involve post-harvest storage which is again like that found in the research entries².

Often the SFT product replaces a tool or technology that is currently being used and can then be used readily without making major changes to the existing system.

In contrast to research SFTs, the SFT products are mostly presented as very easy to use and in most cases, do not require significant learning.

Sometimes, the SFT can be beneficial in ways other than originally developed by the supplier. SFTs are estimated to have effects that can be directly observed by the farmer and they do not require large time investments. Results from SFTs can often be interpreted directly.

Like the research SFTs entries, the stakeholders that are most likely to use product SFTs are contractors.

The main keywords involved with products are: farming equipment and machinery, farming practice and agriculture

production but these are often combined with other options, particularly: production, fertilisation and soil and water management. In contrast keywords related to environmental aspects such as farming-forestry competitiveness, biodiversity and nature management, waste byproduct and residues management, energy management and climate and climate change were less frequently associated with marketed SFTs.

The results from the product entries show quite strong similarities with the list of research entries. Most positive links are in revenue, (soil) biodiversity and variable and input costs. On the other hand, emission reductions are often expected as well as a reduction of stress or fatigue for farmers.

An example of the on-line inventory database for the Dashboard, Overview and Details of a product are given here.

Figure 1 Screen shot of the Inventory Dashboard

Figure 2 Screen shot of the Overview of Technologies

Figure 3 Technologies filtered during search of inventory database.

3.4 Innovation Support.

A program of Workshops in the seven partner countries will start from late February 2017. If, as a researcher, product supplier, potential funder or distributor, you are interested in taking part in Smart AKIS Innovation Workshops, please

contact your Smart AKIS Contact Point.

France: Pauline Bodin, ACTA. pauline.bodin@acta.asso.fr

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Results from these workshops will be available later although attendees will have the opportunity to benefit immediately.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program me under grant agreement no. 696294.

References

- 1 Kernecker M, Knierim A, Wurbs A. 2017. Deliverable 2.2: Report on farmers' needs, innovative ideas and interests. Available from <https://www.smart-akis.com/index.php/network/results/>
- 2 Wolters S, Balafoutis T, Fountas S, van Evert F. 2017. Deliverable 1.2 Research project results on Smart Farming Technology. Available from <https://www.smart-akis.com/index.php/network/results/>
- 3 European Commission DG AGRI – Directorate H.5. Research and Innovation. EIP-AGRI Common format for interactive innovation projects. Accessed January 2017 via <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-common-format>
- 4 Wolters S, Balafoutis T, Fountas S, van Evert F. 2017. Deliverable 1.3 Industry solutions on Smart Farming Technology. Available from <https://www.smart-akis.com/index.php/network/results/>
- 5 Anon 2017. Triggering Smart Farming adoption in Europe – Project Briefing Note. Presented to EC February 2017. Currently not published.